

WHAT DOES MODERN HEBREW CONTINUE? THE CASE OF THE PRESENTATIVES הַנִּנֵּי AND הַרִּינֵי¹

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the continuity between Modern Hebrew and its previous stages, and highlights the important role played by the Hebrew of the Interim period, the period in which the Hebrew was not a spoken language, in the crystallization of Modern Hebrew. The main claim in this article is that when examining whether any linguistic phenomenon in Modern Hebrew is new or continues the previous periods – the Interim period should not be ignored. Examining the origins of the phenomenon only in Classical Hebrew misses the point, and may lead to erroneous conclusions.

The article focuses on the presentative particles hinneni and hareni. These presentatives underwent many changes in the Interim period: their classical functions gradually waned, and other functions became dominant. The syntactic distribution of the forms changed as well, and a new construction, hinneni + infinitive, became quite common. With the advent of Modern Hebrew, the constructions and functions that had prevailed in the Interim period persisted. Conversely, the Classical constructions and functions of the presentatives made their way into Modern Hebrew only if they continued to be used in the Interim period. The process undergone by these presentatives illustrates the continuity between Modern Hebrew and its Interim period sources, and demonstrates the importance of studying this period for understanding the development of Modern Hebrew, and the linguistic processes that occurred during its crystallization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of the study is to show that recognizing and understanding the linguistic development of Hebrew during the Interim period, the period in

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which the Hebrew was not a spoken language,² is crucial to understanding the process of crystallization of Modern Hebrew. In this process the traditional liturgical and literary language was transformed into a modern tongue, used by a newly-created speech community for all its communication needs. The main claim of this article is that when examining whether any linguistic phenomenon in Modern Hebrew is new or continues the previous periods – the Interim period should not be ignored. Examining the origins of the phenomenon only in Classical Hebrew, i.e., Biblical and Mishnaic Hebrew, misses the point, and could lead to wrong conclusions.³

During the Interim period Hebrew was no longer a native spoken language, but it continued to be used. It was articulated in prayer and in the study of religious texts, and remained very much alive as a written language in which numerous works, both religious and secular, were composed.⁴ Moreover, during this period it continued to undergo linguistic change, both under the influence of other languages and as a result of internal development,⁵ and some of these changes later took root in Modern Hebrew as well.

2. This period does not coincide with the medieval period, as it lasts approximately from the third century to the late 19th century.

3. This insight is also evident from other studies, e.g., M. Z. Kaddari, *שלאחר המקרא* (Post-Biblical Hebrew Syntax and Semantics; Ramat-Gan: Bar Ilan University, 1991–1995); G. Birnbaum, “לגלגוליה של המילה 'כדאי'” (The History of the Word *Keday*), in *Sha'arei Lashon: Studies in Hebrew, Aramaic and Jewish Languages Presented to Moshe Bar-Asher*, (ed. Y. Breuer, S. E. Fassberg, A. Maman; Jerusalem: The Bialik Institute, 2007), 2, pp. 31–46; Y. Reshef, T. Zewi, “הבינוני הפועל והבעת הזמנים בעברית” (The Active Participle and Temporal Expression in Hebrew), in *Lěšonenu* 71 (2009), pp. 315–344; K. Dubnov, U. Mor, “בגלל שהיא ברת תוקף: שני פרטים בעברית הקדומה ובעברית הנחשבת בלתי תקינה” (Two Forms in Classical Hebrew and Non-Normative Hebrew), in *Ha'Ivrit* 60 (2012), pp. 99–121; U. Mor, “באם, בכדי,” in *Lěšonenu* 78 (2016), pp. 456–492; R. Stern, “השמועה 'השמועה' (Three Questionable Bets באם, בכדי, נקט ב-)” (The Hebrew Definite Article Introducing a Past-tense Relative Clause), in *Lěšonenu* 80 (2018), pp. 456–492; E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, “אילולי ו'אלמלי' – חלק א' דיאכרוניה לשונית (The History of the Forms 'ilule and 'ilmale – Part I: Linguistic Diachrony), in *Lěšonenu* 81 (2019), pp. 95–115; “חלק ב' – גלגולי מסורות” (Part II: Textual Transmissions), in *Lěšonenu* 82 (2020), pp. 60–78; M. Bar-Ziv Levy, “על תהליכי ההסדרה בהתגבשות העברית החדשה: מילות התנאי הבטל” (Regularization in the Crystallization of Modern Hebrew: The Case of Negative Counterfactual Conditionals), in *Lěšonenu* 83 (2021), pp. 182–202; M. Bar-Ziv Levy, “Regularization in the Crystallization of Modern Hebrew: The Case of Counterfactual Conditionals,” in this volume, and more.

4. E. Doron, M. Rappaport Hovav, Y. Reshef, M. Taube, “Introduction,” in *Language Contact, Continuity and Change in the Genesis of Modern Hebrew* (ed. E. Doron, M. Rappaport Hovav, Y. Reshef, M. Taube; Amsterdam & Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 2019), p. 2; Y. Breuer, *מארמית לעברית: שיטת התרגום בהלכו ראו* (From Aramaic into Hebrew – The Method of Translation in The Book *Hilkhot Re'u*; Jerusalem: The Academy of the Hebrew Language, 2020), pp. 4–6.

5. E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, “לשונות ספרות יהודיות בימי הביניים: הארמית של הזוהר כמקרה מבחן” (Medieval Jewish Literary Languages: The Case of the Aramaic of the Zohar) in *עיונים בלשון ובחוכמת*

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Despite this history, diachronic studies of linguistic phenomena in Modern Hebrew tend to search their sources mostly in Biblical and Mishnaic Hebrew, while overlooking the contribution of the Hebrew in the Interim period. These studies disregard the fact that Classical Hebrew is not the only stage that was familiar to the earliest speakers and writers of Modern Hebrew and influenced their use of the language. All stages of Hebrew, including Hebrew of the Interim period, were available to them, and all of them are reflected in the development of the modern tongue in the early 20th century.⁶ As a matter of fact, the Hebrew of the 18th and 19th centuries is most likely the stage that had the greatest influence on the language of the early speakers and writers, for it was the stage that immediately preceded their own. As a result, it was probably more accessible to them than other stages as a source of linguistic material.⁷

This paper deals with the forms *hinneni* and *hareni*, composed of the presentative particles *hinne* and *hare* followed by the first-person pronoun *-ni*, and with the sources of their usage in Modern Hebrew. It will examine the evolution of their structures and functions in the various stages of Hebrew, and will determine which of these stages is the basis of their use in the early 20th century.

This article discusses three periods:

- The Classic period: Biblical Hebrew and Mishnaic Hebrew
- The Interim period: The period in which the Hebrew was not a spoken language
- Modern Hebrew: From its crystallization period in the late 19th century until the end of the first half of the 20th century

A discussion of these three periods helps to examine the question of the continuity between Modern Hebrew and its sources and to answer the question of which period Early Modern Hebrew continues in this particular phenomenon. The discussion will show that the linguistic differences between Modern Hebrew and Classical Hebrew do not reflect a lack of linguistic

הלשון (Medieval Hebrew and Aramaic: Studies in Language and Grammatical Thought [ed. E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, D. Ya'akov]; Jerusalem: The Academy of the Hebrew Language, 2020), pp. 19–63.

6. Y. Reshef, *Historical Continuity in the Emergence of Modern Hebrew* (Lexington: Maryland, 2019), p. 113; E. Doron et al., “Introduction,” p. 13.

7. See L. Glinert, “למקור העברית החדשה המדוברת: עיונים בתחביר הסמוי של 'לפי הטף' לדוד ילין” (On the Source of Modern Colloquial Hebrew: The Covert Syntax of Yellin’s Primer) in *Lěšonenu* 55 (1991), pp.107–126.

continuity but precisely the opposite.⁸ If the expressions under discussion underwent considerable change during the Interim period, and the changes, which persisted throughout the Interim period, were inherited by Modern Hebrew, this is blatantly an example of continuity rather than discontinuity.

On the other hand, the same linguistic phenomenon that appears in both Classical and Modern Hebrew does not necessarily indicate continuity between Classical Hebrew and Modern Hebrew. If this phenomenon continued to appear throughout the Interim period, the immediate linguistic continuity is rather with the Interim period, and not with the classical period.

The analysis of the presentative in the article has two aspects:

- a. An identification of the syntactic structures in which the presentatives appear and a description of their emergence from a linguistic perspective.
- b. An analysis of the function of the various structures and the semantic development that took place in their uses.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research method varies according to the period studied. The study of the Classical period, relies mostly on previous studies of the presentatives, and on the data that could be located at the Even-Shoshan Concordance⁹ and Dicta website,¹⁰ and in the data base Ma'agarim of the Historical Dictionary Project.¹¹ The analysis of the Interim Period is based on an original study based for the most part on a comprehensive examination of *hinneni* and *hareni* as they appear in the corpus of Responsa literature compiled by Bar Ilan University's Responsa Project. The section deals with Modern Hebrew relies on data gleaned from the following sources: The data base Ma'agarim of the Historical Dictionary Project, the Historical Jewish Press website,¹² the corpus of the Language Committee letters,¹³ the Ben Yehuda Project,¹⁴ Knesset

8. See also Y. Reshef, *Historical Continuity*, p. 113.

9. A. Even-Shoshan, קונקורדנציה חדשה לתורה נביאים וכתובים (A New Concordance of the Bible; Jerusalem: Kiryat Sefer, 1988).

10. <https://search.dicta.org.il/>

11. <https://maagarim.hebrew-academy.org.il/Pages/PMain.aspx>

12. <https://www.nli.org.il/he/newspapers/search>

13. See R. Stern, "Hebrew Definite Article," p. 478

14. <https://benyehuda.org/>

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minutes from the first decade of the State of Israel,¹⁵ the heTenTen14 corpus,¹⁶ and Google Books Ngram.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 3 will describe *hinne* and *hare* main functions in Classical Hebrew, namely in Biblical and Mishnaic Hebrew.¹⁷ Section 4 will present the changes they underwent in Hebrew of the Interim period: Section 4.1 will focus on their functions during this period, describing the meanings that were discarded, those that grew more prevalent and the new meanings that developed, while Section 4.2 will focus on the constructions in which they appeared, including a new construction that emerged during the Interim period itself. Section 5 will discuss the sources of Modern Hebrew and the stages that influenced it in the context under discussion. It will also examine the evolution of the forms in Modern Hebrew, which involved the regularization of the materials inherited from the previous stages of the language.

3. THE GRAMMAR OF THE FORMS IN CLASSICAL HEBREW

Hinne and *hare* are presentative particles whose function is to call the hearer's attention to some element (thing, person or event) in the world or to some linguistic element in the discourse.¹⁸ *Hinne* appended with a first-person singular pronoun, *hinne*, occurs in the Bible.¹⁹ In Mishnaic Hebrew *hinne*

15. <https://m.knesset.gov.il/activity/plenum/pages/plenumallprotocols.aspx>

16. See <https://www.sketchengine.eu/hetenten-hebrew-corpus/#toggle-id-1>

17. There are subtle differences between the use of the presentatives in these two Classical periods, but for the purposes of this article, which aims to present a general picture of their use in this period, I will disregard these differences and describe both periods together.

18. A. A. Bloch, *Studies in Arabic Syntax and Semantics* (Wiesbaden: O. Harrassowitz, 1986), p. 54; U. Mor, “הרי אתה דן: מילות ההצגה 'הרי' ו'הלא' בלשון חז"ל על פי כתב יד וסיקן לספרי במדבר” (Two Presentative Particles in Mishnaic Hebrew According to Ms. Ebr. 32.2 to 'Sifré on Numbers'), in *Lěšonenu* 68 (2006), p. 209; H. Gzella, “Presentatives,” in *Encyclopedia of Hebrew Language and Linguistics* (ed. G. Khan; Leiden: Brill, 2013).

19. Among the studies that examined the function of *hinne* in Biblical Hebrew are S. Kogut, “למשמעה ולמעמדה התחבירי של 'הנה' בעברית המקראית” (On the Meaning and Syntactical Status of הנה in Biblical Hebrew), in *Language Studies* 2–3 (1987), pp. 245–258; T. Zewi, “ההסבות התחביריות הכרוכות במבנה הפונקציונלי” (Syntactical Modifications Reflecting the Functional Structure of the Sentence in Biblical Hebrew; Ph.D. dissertation; The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 1992), pp. 204–210; O. R. Schwarzwald, “ה'הנה' ו'הנה' בתרגומי לאדינו ובתרגומי ספרד: היבטים מילוניים ותחביריים” (Hebrew *hinne*, *wəhinne* and *hen* in the Ladino and Medieval Spanish Bible Translation of Genesis), in *Carmillim* 10 (2014), pp. 113–131; E. Cohen, “Presentatives in comparative view: Biblical Hebrew and Neo-Aramaic,” in *From Tur Abdin to Hadramawt – Semitic Studies – Festschrift in Honour of Bo Isaksson on the Occasion of His Retirement* (ed. T. Davidovich, A. Lahdo, T. Lindquist; Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2014), pp. 23–38 and numerous other studies referenced in these sources.

was superseded by *hare*,²⁰ so that *hinneni* was superseded by *hareni* or by the equivalent with an independent pronoun, *hare ani*.²¹

3.1 Function

In Classical Hebrew *hinneni* and *hareni* had three main functions, all of them stemming from their basic use as presentatives (i.e., presenting or pointing to something in the concrete sense of the term):

- Deictic function
- Rhetorical function in futurate (expected future)²² utterances
- Rhetorical function in utterances expressing immediacy

A. Deictic function

The basic use of the presentatives *hinneni* and *hareni* is to point to the speaker's location: *hinne ani, hare ani* 'here I am':

1. וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהֵי אַבְרָהָם וַיֹּאמֶר הִנְנִי
“Abraham”! And he said, “Here I am.” (Gen 22:1).
2. הֲרִינִי לְפָנֶיךָ כְּכֵלִי מִלֵּא בּוֹשָׁה וְכִלְמָה
Behold I am before Thee like a vessel full of shame and reproach (*b. Yoma* 87b).

B. Rhetorical function in futurate (expected future) utterances

Futurate utterances refer to events which are expected to occur in the future. In these utterances the presentatives perform confirmation of what is said in the sentence: the future action is certain to occur.²³

3. הֲנִנִּי מְפְרֶךָ וְהִרְבִּיתֶךָ וְנִתְתִּיךָ לְקַהֲלֵ עַמִּים
Behold, I will make you fruitful and multiply you, and I will make of you a multitude of people (Gen 48:4).
4. הֲנִנִּי מְבִיא מִחַר אַרְבָּה בְּגִבְלֶךָ

20. On the function of *hare* in Mishnaic Hebrew, see U. Mor, “Two Presentative Particles.”

21. U. Mor, “Two Presentative Particles,” and references therein. On the omission of the glottal stop and the merging of the forms *hare* and *ani*, see N. Berggrün, עיונים בלשון העברית (Studies in The Hebrew Language; Jerusalem: The Academy of the Hebrew Language, 1995), pp. 108–112; Y. Breuer, העברית בתלמוד הבבלי: לפי חכמי (The Hebrew in the Babylonian Talmud According to the Manuscripts of Tractate Pesahim; Jerusalem: Magnes, 2002), p. 92; S. Sharvit, פרקי מחקר בלשון חכמים (Studies in Mishnaic Hebrew; Jerusalem: Bialik Institute, 2008), p. 7.

22. On futurate see J. L. Bybee, R. Perkins, W. Pagliuca, *The Evolution of Grammar: Tense, Aspects, and Modality in the Languages of the World* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1994), pp. 249–251.

23. H. Gzella, “Presentatives.”

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Behold, tomorrow I will bring locusts into your territory (Exod 10:4).

5. הריני נושה בו שמנה מאות זוז

And now I am his creditor for eight hundred zuz (*b. B. Meṣi'a* 77b).

In these utterances the speaker – either God, as in examples 3–4,²⁴ or a human actor, as in example 5 – makes a commitment or expresses an intention to undertake a future action. The verb in these utterances usually takes the participle form, but the time referred to is future; that is, the speech time precedes the event time.²⁵ This is evident from the context, and occasionally also from adverbs within the sentence, as in 4.²⁶ Here too, as in the case of the deictic use, *hinnei* and *hareni* comprise two morphemes, each with its own meaning. The presentative particle expresses the certainty of the future action, whereas the pronoun marks the subject of the sentence.²⁷

This extension of the presentative function, from physical presenting to underscoring the certainty of an action, is familiar from many languages, including from the Arabic cognate of *hinne*, *إِنَّ* (*inna*).²⁸

The rhetorical function in futurate utterances is the most prevalent use of these forms in Classical Hebrew.

C. Rhetorical function in utterances expressing immediacy

The third function of the presentatives in *hinnei* and *hareni* in Classical Hebrew is the rhetorical use of expressing immediacy. This occurs in

24. P. Humbert, “La formule hébraïque en *hineni* suivi d’un participle,” in *Revue des Études Juives* 97 (1934), pp. 58–64; H. Gzella, “Presentatives.”

25. Definitions according to H. Reichenbach, *Elements of Symbolic Logic* (London: Macmillan, 1947), §51; C. S. Smith, *The Parameter of Aspect* (Dordrecht: Kluwer, 1991); N. Hornstein, *As Time Goes By: Tense and Universal Grammar* (Cambridge, Mass: The MIT Press, 1990).

26. The futurate use of participles is familiar cross-linguistically, including from Mishnaic Hebrew. (see J. L. Bybee, R. Perkins, W. Pagliuca, *The Evolution of Grammar: Tense, Aspects, and Modality in the Languages of the World*, [Chicago: Chicago University Press, 2014], pp. 249–251; B. Copley, “The Plan’s the thing: Deconstructing Futurate Meanings,” in *Linguistic Inquiry* 39.2 [2008], p. 262; E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, “Towards a Reconsideration of the Tense-Aspect-Mood System of Tannaitic Hebrew,” in *Studies in Mishnaic Hebrew and Related Fields: Proceedings of the Yale Symposium on Mishnaic Hebrew, May 2014* [ed. E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, A. J. Koller; Jerusalem: Yale University & The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 2017], pp. 85–87). On the association of the participle with present time in later stages of the language, see Y. Reshef, T. Zewi, “The Active Participle.”

27. For this analysis of the pronoun in *hinnei*, see A. Niccacci, “Polotsky’s Contribution to the Egyptian Verb-System, with a Comparison to Biblical Hebrew,” *Egyptian, Semitic and General Grammar: Studies in Memory of HJ Polotsky* (ed. G. Goldenberg, A. Shisha-Halevy; Jerusalem: Israel Academy of Sciences and Humanities, 2009), fn. 52.

28. A. A. Bloch, *Studies in Arabic*, pp. 68–69, 102, 113.

utterances where the action takes place immediately after the moment of utterance (6, 7) or simultaneously with it (8, 9).

6. ועתה הנני הולך לעמי

And now, indeed, I am going to my people (Num 24:14).

7. אמ' לו ר' עקיבא: הרי אני מוסיף על דברי

Said R. Akiba to him: Behold, I will add to your words (b. *Šabb.* 68b).

8. הנני נשבעתי בשמי הגדול

Behold, I have sworn by My great name (Jer 44:26).

9. הריני נשבע

I shall swear (b. *Šebbu.* 39a).

This use is related to the previous one, because when an action takes place in close proximity to speech time, its occurrence can be stated with a high degree of certainty. In this case the presentatives do not emphasize the certainty of the action but rather its proximity to speech time. The close proximity entails that the speaker's intention to perform what he states that it about to take place (“here, I am doing it right now”).²⁹

The function of expressing immediacy is evident in explicit performative utterances, in which the utterance and the action are one and the same.³⁰ Therefore, some have characterized *hinne* and *hare* in such contexts as performative markers.³¹ But, as stated above, their function is in fact broader,

29. The present time and immediacy connotations of *hinne* are even recognized in the Midrash: ויאמר ה' אל משה הנני ממטיר לכם – ר' יהוש' או': אמ' המק' למשה: הרי אני נגלה מיד. אינו מעכב. 'Then the Lord said to Moses, Behold, I will rain bread from heaven for you – Rabbi Yehoshua says: God said to Moses, I will appear immediately. He does not delay' (*Mek. Beshalah* 2). This quotation demonstrates how Mishnaic Hebrew translates the Biblical *hinne* into *hare ani*. On the phenomenon of Biblical Hebrew translated into Mishnaic Hebrew in the Midrash Halacha, see e.g., M. Kahana, “עיון בפרשנות הפרשנות ובההדרת המקורות” (A Study in the Exegesis of Exegesis – ‘שיקור’ ו’שינוי’ – ‘שיקור’ and ‘שינוי’), in *Lěšonenu* 55 (1990), pp. 77–88; A. Bendavid, לשון מקרא ולשון חכמים (Biblical Hebrew and Mishnaic Hebrew; Tel Aviv: Dvir, 1967), pp. 335–366 (On this phenomenon in the context of *hinne* and *hare*, see p. 343).

30. Explicit performatives have been defined in different ways; I follow J. R. Searle, “How Performatives Work,” in *Linguistics & Philosophy* 12 (1989), pp. 536–538. The bare form *hare* also appears in performatives in Mishnaic Hebrew; see M. Azar, תחביר לשון המשנה (The Syntax of Mishnaic Hebrew; Jerusalem: The Academy of the Hebrew Language, 1995), p. 161 and U. Mor, “Two Presentative Particles,” pp. 217–218.

31. See e.g., M. Ariel, “Three Grammaticalization Paths for the Development of Person Verbal Agreement in Hebrew,” in *Discourse and Cognition: Bridging the Gap* (ed. J. P. Koenig; Stanford: Stanford University, 1998), pp. 101–102.

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since it is also evident in declarative utterances, where the speaker announces his intention to perform a certain action straight away.³²

While the rhetorical function of emphasizing certainty is one of the common roles of the presentatives in Classical Hebrew, the function of marking immediacy is rarer. When *hinnen* and *haren* are used in this manner, they are naturally restricted to utterances expressing present time.

It is important to note that the functions listed above belong to the presentative particles in *hinnen* and *haren*, not to the pronoun, which refers to the subject of the sentence. Hence, the three functions are evident even when the pronoun is not cliticized to the presentative but is independent, as shown by the following examples:

10. הִנֵּה אֲנִי וְהַיְלָדִים אֲשֶׁר נָתַן לִי יְהוָה לְאֹתוֹת וּלְמוֹפְתִים בְּיִשְׂרָאֵל.
Here am I and the children whom the Lord has given me. We are for signs and wonders in Israel (Isa 8:18) – Deictic function.
11. הִנֵּה אֲנִי מְבִיא בְּכֶם רוּחַ וְחַיִּיתֶם.
Surely I will cause breath to enter into you, and you shall live (Ezek 37:5) – Marker of futurate action.
12. וַיֹּאמֶר יִשְׂרָאֵל אֶל יוֹסֵף הִנֵּה אֲנִי מֵת.
Behold, I am dying (Gen 48:21) – Marker of immediacy.

In conclusion, as demonstrated in Table 1, *hinnen* and *haren* in Classical Hebrew appear in utterances expressing present time and futurate time and have three main functions:

Function/ period	Classic Hebrew	
Deictic Function	+	'Here I am'
Marker of immediacy	+	'I now act'
Marker of futurate action	+	'I will definitely act'

Table 1: The function of the forms in Classic Hebrew

32. On the face of it, these two types of utterances (performatives and declaratives) are not so closely related. Yet the two types of utterance are more similar than they appear, since explicit performatives verbs are generally analyzed as performing two speech acts simultaneously: (1) **Declaration**, (2) a speech act that is identical to the content of the performative verb (e.g., warning, request, promise). See J. R. Searle, D. Vanderveken, in *Foundations of Illocutionary Logic* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1985) and J. R. Searle, "How Performatives Work," pp. 535–558. On the connection between these two kinds of utterances and on the issue of immediacy, see R. Stern, "הכתיבה הפורמלית בעברית: שונות לשונית להתגבשות סטנדרט: הכתיבה הפורמלית בעברית" (The Formal Writing in Early Modern Hebrew: From Diversity to Standardization; Ph.D. dissertation; The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, [in preparation]).

3.2 Syntactic Structure

In Classical Hebrew, *hinneni* appears in 4 syntactic structures:

- *hinneni* + participle (126 occurrences)³³
- *hinneni* alone (25 occurrences)
- *hinneni* + nominal predicate (24 occurrences)
- *hinneni* + future form (5 occurrences)

4. THE GRAMMAR OF THE FORMS IN THE INTERIM PERIOD

The Hebrew of the Interim period, the period in which the Hebrew was not a spoken language, does not flow directly from Mishnaic Hebrew. Since Hebrew was no longer a spoken tongue in this period, its grammar is not a straightforward continuation of the preceding stage, but integrates several different grammars from various stages of the language.³⁴ In the Interim period the Biblical *hinneni* came back into use, alongside the Mishnaic *harenī*, and over time both became increasingly prevalent. However, the change they underwent was not confined to their prevalence; their meanings, and the constructions in which they appeared, changed as well.³⁵

In the Interim period, 2 classical functions continued to be used:

- Deictic function
- Marker of immediacy. This function became the main function of the presentatives

One classic function disappeared during this period:

- Marker of futurate action

In addition, in this period 2 new functions began to appear:

- Copula
- Readiness to perform an action

As for the syntactic structures 4 classical structures continued to be used:

33. The numbers here refer to Biblical Hebrew because it is difficult to give absolute numbers in Rabbinic Hebrew.

34. E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, "Medieval Jewish Literary Languages," pp. 31–32; E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, "'ilule and 'ilmale," pp. 108–109, 74–75.

35. All the conclusions presented in this section of the paper are based on a comprehensive examination of *hinneni* and *harenī* as they appear in the corpus of Responsa literature compiled by Bar Ilan University's Responsa Project. The discussion here presents a general overview of their distribution and main functions in this literature. However, given the scope of the corpus, there may be rare functions or constructions that are not described here.

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- *hinneni* + participle
- *hinneni* + nominal predicate
- *hinneni* alone
- *hinneni* + past/future form (rare structure)
In addition, in this period new structure began to appear:
- *hinneni* + infinitive

The next two sections are dedicated to a description of these changes. I will provide proposals as to what brought about these changes, and will emphasize some connections between the various developments.

4.1 Function

In the Interim period, the presentatives in *hinneni* and *hareni* continued to perform the basic deictic role, but the rhetorical function of signaling certainty gradually vanished, while the rhetoric function of signaling immediacy became more prevalent. As will be explained below, the two changes essentially stem from a single development.

In the Interim period the association of the presentatives with immediate action became stronger,³⁶ and the function of marking immediacy, previously rare, became one of their main uses. It occurs in both explicit performative utterances (13) and in declarative ones (14):

13. **הנני מודיע** [...] שהכתב שנשתלח אלי משמו [של הפרנס הנעלה] שהיה שקר וזיוף.
I hereby announce [...] that the letter sent to me on behalf of [the honorable elder] was a lie and a forgery. (Spain, 13th century)³⁷
14. **והנני משיב** לשאלתיך כאשר יורוני מן השמים.
And I hereby reply to your question as I was instructed from above. (Palestine, 15th century)³⁸

36. Kahn calls this “imminent future force,” see L. Kahn, “Grammatical Similarities between Nineteenth Century Hasidic and Maskilic Hebrew Narratives,” in *Hebrew Studies* 53 (2012), pp. 197–198. See also K. Dubnov, “דקדוק 'אביעזר' – על סוגיות תחביר אחדות באוטוביוגרפיה של המשכיל מרדכי אהרן גינצבורג” (The Grammar of 'Aviezer' – On Several Syntactic Issues Themes in the Autobiography of M.A. Ginzburg), in *Jewish Speech* 7 (2017), pp. 56–57.

37. R. Shlomo ibn Aderet, *שאלות ותשובות הרשב"א* (Responsa of Rashba; Jerusalem: Machon Yerushalayim, 1997), 2: §29, p. 27.

38. R. Joseph Karo, *ספר אבקת רוכל* (Responsa Avkat Roxel; Thessaloniki: M Nachman and D. Israelija, 1791), §37, p. 26b.

As stated, in these utterances the action is either synonymous with the articulation itself or follows it immediately; in other words, speech time and event time are simultaneous or nearly so. The demonstrative component of the presentative became associated more strongly with immediate action because an action can be pointed to only if it takes place right in front of us. This component thus enabled *hareni* and *hinnen* to become markers of immediacy.

However, since in the Interim period the presentatives became strongly associated with immediacy, they could no longer occur in future-tense sentences. As a result, they gradually lost the rhetorical function of emphasizing the certainty of a future action that had been prevalent in Classical Hebrew. Thus, in this period sentences in these constructions are restricted to present-tense utterances, usually ones in which the action immediately follows the act of articulation. In the rare cases where they co-occur with future- or past-tense verbs, these verbs refer to present time, and the presentatives convey a sense of immediacy:

15. **והנני אכתוב** לך מקצת דבריהם בלשונם

And I now write [lit. will write] to you some of their statements in their own words. (Spain, 13th century)³⁹

16. **והנני באתי** כמזכיר וכמזהיר

And I now come [lit. came] to remind and to warn. (Ashkenaz, 15th century)⁴⁰

In addition to these changes, in the Interim period there was another major change in the function of the presentatives. This period saw the emergence of a completely new function of these forms: *hinnen* and *hareni* underwent semantic reanalysis: their semantic meaning was bleached and they became a purely functional form – a copula indicating present time in nominal sentences, e.g.:

17. **ואני הנני** החלש והעני

And I am the weak and the poor. (Spain, 14th century)⁴¹

18. **ואני הנני** מסכים אחריהם

39. R. Shlomo ibn Aderet, שאלות ותשובות הרשב"א (Responsa of Rashba; Jerusalem: Machon Yerushalayim, 1998), 4: §262, p. 132.

40. R. Jacob Weil, שאלות ותשובות (Responsa of Mahari Weil; Jerusalem: safra, 1959), §140, p. 91.

41. R. Isaac ben Sheshet, שאלות ותשובות בר ששת (Responsa of Rivash; New-York: Reinman Seforim Center, 1954), § 272, p. 152.

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And I am in agreement with them. (Ashkenaz, 13th century)⁴²

19. **הנני העני ממעש**

I am the poor in deeds.⁴³

These copulas are not restricted to first person but also appear in second and third:

20. **אתה הנך גבוה הרבה הרבה**

You are very, very noble. (Ukraine, 18th century)⁴⁴

21. **איך...קרא למרנא ורבנא כהנא רבה חמור הננו כתוב וחתום שם בכתב הקהלות**

How he...called our rabbi and teacher a donkey is written and sealed there in the community chronicles. (Turkey and Greece, 16th century)⁴⁵

The predicate of these sentences is a noun or participle, which are not inflected for tense or person, and *hinneni/hareni* serve to carry this information instead.⁴⁶ Conversely, in past- and future-tense sentences, tense and person are marked on the verb, so there is no need to employ the presentative in this role. Presentatives serving as copulas can appear in any present-time utterance, not just in utterances where the action that takes place in close proximity to the moment of speech.

The copular presentatives of the Interim period could appear either with an independent pronoun (17, 18, 20) or without one (19). Thus, they are similar to Hebrew inflected verbs in the Interim period, which, in first and second person, can likewise appear either with an independent pronoun in subject

42. R. Meir of Rothenburg, שאלות ותשובות מהר"ם מרוטנברג (Responsa of Maharam of Rothenberg; Jerusalem: Machon Yerushalayim, 2015), 3: §540, p. 353. It should be noted that the use of the phrase *ani hinneni* was probably inspired by the Biblical text, which includes five instances of this phrase, all of them introduced by the conjunctive *vav* which also appears in most of the examples from the Responsa literature. However, in the Biblical examples *hinneni* never serves as a copula but has a deictic function, e.g., **וְאָנִי הַנְּנִי בְיַדְכֶם עָשׂוּ לִי** 'As for me, here I am, in your hand; do with me as seems good and proper to you' (Jer 26:14), or the rhetorical function of expressing commitment to a future action, e.g., **וְאָנִי הַנְּנִי מִקִּים אֶת בְּרִיתִי** 'And as for Me, behold, I establish My covenant with you and with your descendants after you' (Gen 9:9).

43. Prayer for Rosh Hashanah and Yom Kippur.

44. R. Hayyim Tyrer, באר מים חיים (Be'er Mayim Hayim; Chernivtsi: Johan Eckhardt und Sohn, 1849), Deuteronomy, P. 7a.

45. Benjamin Ze'ev of Arta, בנימין זאב (Responsa Binyamin Ze'ez, Venice: Daniel Bomberg, 1539), §249, p. 350b.

46. On the analysis of the copula as carrying the inflection of the sentence, see E. Doron, "Verbless Predicates in Hebrew," (Ph.D. dissertation; University of Texas at Austin, 1983).

position (*ani ekhtov oto* 'I will write it') or without an overt element in subject position (*ekhtov oto* 'I will write it').⁴⁷

The use of the copular presentative is clearly illustrated by these minimal pairs:

22. אדון לפניך על כל דברי האגרת הזאת השנית

I will discuss before you all the statements of this second letter.⁴⁸

23. וכן דנתי לפני מורנו הרמב"ן ז"ל

And so I ruled before our teacher, the Ramban of blessed memory.⁴⁹

24. הריני דן לפניך על דברי שניכם

I rule now before you the statements of the two of you.⁵⁰

When the clause contains an inflected verb, there is no need for a presentative particle serving as copula (22, 23). But when the verb is in the participle form, which does not inflect for tense and person, the presentative is used to provide this information (24).

The copular use of the presentative apparently emerged under the influence of the languages spoken in the Jews' surroundings during the Middle Ages. These languages disallow sentences lacking an overt finite element. Therefore, in sentences with a nominal predicate they insert a copula to indicate the tense. The presentatives in the examples above perform the same role. Indeed, most instances of copular presentatives are from regions where the spoken languages were Spanish, Greek, Turkish, Yiddish and German, which mandate a copula in sentences with a nominal predicate. Quite possibly, the use of presentatives as copulas was facilitated by their close

47. See L. Kahn, *A Grammar of the Eastern European Hasidic Hebrew Tale* (Leiden: Brill, 2015), pp. 113–114. The Classical Hebrew verb in first and second person appears without an overt pronoun in subject position, see P. Joüon, T. Muraoka, *A Grammar of Biblical Hebrew* (2nd ed.; Roma: Editrice Pontificio Istituto biblico, 2006), §146a; B. K. Waltke, M. O'Connor, *An Introduction to Biblical Hebrew Syntax* (Winona Lake, Ind: Eisenbrauns, 1990), §16.3.2; Ch. Cohen, "ההיצב התחבירי של הכינויים בלשון התנאים" (AE Morpho-syntax of the pronouns in tannatic Hebrew; Ph.D. dissertation; Tel Aviv University, 1992), pp. 1–13; M. Azar, *The Syntax of Mishnaic Hebrew*, pp. 67–69; U. Mor, עברית יהודאית: לשון התעודות העבריות ממדבר יהודה בין המרד הגדול (Judean Hebrew: the Language of the Hebrew Documents from Judea between the First and Second Revolts; Jerusalem: Academy of the Hebrew Language, 2015), pp. 267–269.

48. R. Shlomo ibn Aderet, שאלות ותשובות הרשב"א (Responsa of Rashba; Jerusalem: Machon Yerushalayim, 1998), 5: §2281, p. 188.

R. Shlomo ibn Aderet, שאלות ותשובות הרשב"א (Responsa of Rashba; Jerusalem: Machon Yerushalayim, 2001), 7: §389, p. 129.

50. R. Shlomo ibn Aderet, שאלות ותשובות הרשב"א (Responsa of Rashba; Jerusalem: Machon Yerushalayim, 1997), 3: §8, p. 14.

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association with present time, which made them natural candidates to serve as grammatical markers of present tense.⁵¹

Unlike the uses of *hinneri* and *haren*i in Classical Hebrew, their new role, as copulas, does not stem from their basic function of presentation, but emerged under the influence of other languages. However, for these forms to be interpreted as copulas, foreign influence is not enough. Their semantic reanalysis as copulas was necessarily preceded by a syntactic reanalysis.⁵² In Classical Hebrew, *hinneri* and *haren*i were composed of two morphemes, a presentative particle and a dependent pronoun, and the function of the presentative alone determined the function of the entire lexeme. However, to become copulas, *hinneri* and *haren*i were reanalyzed as a single morphological unit inflected for tense and person.

This syntactic reanalysis is evident from the fact that these forms could no longer be separated into two lexemes. To be precise, the combinations *hinne ani/anoxi* and *hare ani*, found in Classical Hebrew, occur in the Interim period as well, but only when serving in the Classical functions, e.g.:

25. אמר ר' מנחם...לישמעאל...הנה אני עומד פה

Rabbi Menachem...said to...Ishmael: Here I am, standing here. (Greece, 16th century)⁵³ – Deictic function.

26. והנה אני משיב על ראשון במה שכתבתי

And I hereby reply to the first [point] in what I wrote. (Algeria, 14th and 15th century)⁵⁴ – Immediacy marker in a declarative utterance.

27. הנה אני נותן כל נכסי לה"ר מרדכי

51. The question of the copula in various stages of Hebrew is a complicated one, see T. Muraoka, "Copula: Biblical Hebrew," M. Azar, "Copula: Rabbinic Hebrew," G. Danon, "Copula: Modern Hebrew," in *Encyclopedia of Hebrew Language and Linguistics* (ed. G. Khan; Leiden: Brill, 2013) and references therein. This study does not presume to resolve it. The issue of copular presentatives followed by a clitic pronoun likewise requires a more extensive investigation than allowed by the scope of the present study. On *hinne* and *hare* accompanied by a pronoun, see also M. Ariel, "Three Grammaticalization Paths."

52. On syntactic and semantic reanalysis see E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, "A Formal Approach to Reanalysis: The Case of a Negative Counterfactual Marker," in *Proceedings of the Linguistic Society of America* 5.2 (2020), pp. 34–50.

53. R. Samuel ben Moses de Medina, שאלות ותשובות מהרשד"ם (Responsa of Maharashdam; Lemberg: Ab. Nis. Suess und B. L. Necheles, 1862), 2: §18, p. 11a.

54. R. Simeon ben Zemah Duran, ספר התשב"ץ (Responsa of Tashbez; Lemberg: U. W. Salat, 1891), 2: §19, p. 5a.

I hereby bequeath all my assets to Rabbi Mordechai. (Algeria, 14th and 15th century)⁵⁵ – Immediacy marker in a performative utterance.

Copular presentatives, on the other hand, cannot be separated into two independent units, since they have been reanalyzed as a single unit. Just as the form *halaxti* 'I walked' cannot be separated into *halax ani*, copular *hinneni* cannot be replaced by *hinne ani*.⁵⁶ Although this reanalysis was probably motivated by foreign influence, this kind of reanalysis shows that Hebrew underwent dynamic development in the Interim period, despite being a written language rather than a spoken one.⁵⁷

Another new function of *hinneni* that evolved in the Interim period was that of indicating readiness to perform an action.⁵⁸ This meaning developed under the influence of the Rabbinic interpretation of the following Biblical verses:

28. וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהֵי אַבְרָהָם וַיֹּאמֶר הִנְנִי... וַיִּקְרָא אֱלֹהֵי מְלֶאכֶּה ה' מִן הַשָּׁמַיִם וַיֹּאמֶר אַבְרָהָם אַבְרָהָם. וַיֹּאמֶר הִנְנִי

And said to him, “Abraham!” And he said, “Here I am.” ...But the Angel of the Lord called to him from heaven and said, “Abraham, Abraham!” So he said, “Here I am.” (Gen 22:1, 11).

The Midrash interprets *hinneni* in Abraham's statements as an expression of his willingness to perform what is demanded of him.⁵⁹ This interpretation was adopted by Rashi in his commentary on the Torah (29), which probably accounts for its prevalence in the Interim period (30, 31).⁶⁰

55. R. Simeon ben Zemah Duran, ספר התשב"ץ (Responsa of Tashbez; Lemberg: U. W. Salat, 1891), 4: §33, p. 12a.

56. I thank Elitzur Bar-Asher Siegal for this insight.

57. For a comprehensive discussion about the developments in Hebrew in the Interim period, see E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, “Medieval Jewish Literary Languages” and Bar-Asher Siegal in this issue.

58. On the readiness function of this lexeme, already apparent in the Bible, and on its origins, see S. Kogut, “הנה in Biblical Hebrew,” p. 251.

59. See e.g., Gen. Rab. 55, 6.

60. On Rashi's extensive impact on the understanding of Hebrew in the Interim period, see e.g., A. Grossmann, רש"י (Rashi; Jerusalem: The Zalman Shazar, 2006), p. 77; Ch. Gamliel, “פירוש רש"י לתורה כמפעל,” (The Contribution of Rashi's Torah Commentary to the Hebrew Language), in *Sha'arei Lashon: Studies in Hebrew, Aramaic and Jewish Languages Presented to Moshe Bar-Asher* (ed. Y. Breuer, S. E. Fassberg, A. Maman; Jerusalem: Bialik Institute, 2007), pp. 125–126; A. Shaveh, “על הקשיים בזיהוי,” (On the Difficulties in Identifying Lexical Innovations of Medieval Writers: Rashi as a Test Case), in *Medieval Hebrew and Aramaic: Studies in Language and*

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29. “הנני” – לשון זימון

“*Hinneni*” – an expression of readiness = “I am willing and ready.”⁶¹

30. ואני כל ימי צבאי הנני לכל אשר יצוני

And I, all the days of my life, am ready to do anything I am commanded to do. (Turkey, 15th and 16th century)⁶²

31. ויצוה לתקן והנני למצותו

And he commanded to amend it, and I am ready to do his bidding. (Pressburg, 18th century)⁶³

In the Interim period this type of *hinneni* appears mainly in the expressions *hinneni levakashato*, *hinneni lidvarav*, *hinneni lifqudato* 'I am at his bidding/command,' and others like them, which are common in the Responsa literature from the 18th century onward.

Table 2 summarizes the development of the presentatives' functions during the Interim period:

Function/ period	Classic Hebrew	Interim period	Notes
Deictic Function	+	+	
Marker of immediacy	+	+	This function became very common compared to Classic Hebrew
Marker of futurate action	+	–	
Copula	–	+	
Readiness to perform an action	–	+	

Table 2: The function of the forms in the Interim Period

Grammatical Thought (ed. E. A. Bar-Asher Siegal, D. Ya'akov; Jerusalem: The Academy of the Hebrew Language, 2020), p. 238.

61. Rashi on Gen 22:1.

62. R. 'Eliyahu Mizrahi, ספר שאלות ותשובות ר' אליהו מזרחי (Responsa of R. 'Eliyahu Mizrahi; Jerusalem: Darom, 1982), §74, p. 243.

63. R. Moses Sofer, ספר חתם סופר (Responsa of Hatam Sofer; New-York: J. E. Grossman, 1958), §193, p. 73a.

4.2 Syntactic Structure and Distribution

Along with the change in the function of the presentatives, the Interim period saw a change in their syntactic structure and distribution. The first development is the one already mentioned above: the emergence of the copular use, which involved a reanalysis of the presentative and dependent pronoun as a copula inflected for tense and person. But in addition, the forms began to appear in a new construction that didn't previously exist. In both Classical and Interim-period Hebrew, *hinneni* is generally followed by a participle, *hinenni* + participle or by a nominal predicate. The data available today indicates that in 16th century Italy, *hinneni* also began appearing with verbs in the infinitive: *hinneni* + infinitive:⁶⁴

32. **הנני להחזיק בנער משה בנך יצ'ו ולהדריכו בדרך ישרה**

I will teach the boy Moshe, your son, God preserve him, and guide him on the right path. (Italy, 16th century)⁶⁵

33. **והנני להורות בו היתר גמורה**

And hereby I rule it to be permissible. (Italy, 15th and 16th century)⁶⁶

Here too, *hinneni* performs the function of carrying the inflection, because the infinitive verb does not inflect. In other words, *hinneni* again functions as a copula indicating person and time, while the infinitive expresses the lexical content of the predicate. Predictably, like other constructions with copular *hinneni*, this construction disallows replacing *hinneni* with the sequence *hinne ani*, since the copula is a single unit that cannot be divided.

64. *Hareni* + infinitive emerged later in the 17th century, according to a search in the Responsa Project corpus. In Ma'agarim we also find three earlier instances of *hinneni* + infinitive, all of them expressing readiness to act, e.g., **הנני לשהוט. הנני ליהרג. הנני לכהונה. הנני למלכות.** *Vayyomer hinneni* – [means] I am ready for the priesthood, for the kingship, for the slaughter, for the killing [i.e., “I am ready to slaughter and to kill”] (*Tanh. Vayyera* 44). All these examples feature *hinneni* followed by an infinitive verb expressing the action that the speaker is willing to perform. As a result, they appear similar to the new construction we are discussing, but in actual fact they are completely different in their structure. In these examples *hinneni*, meaning “[am] ready,” serves as the predicate and the infinitive serves as its complement. Conversely, in the new construction, the combination *hinneni* + infinitive serves as the predicate, in which *hinenni* carries the inflection and the infinitive conveys the lexical meaning. Instances of *hinneni* + infinitive conveying readiness to act are found sporadically in texts from the Interim period as well.

65. Y. Boksenboim, *אגרות יהודי איטליה* (Letters of Jews in Italy; Jerusalem: Ben Zvi Institute, 1994), p. 71.

66. R. Meir Katzenellenbogen, *הא לכם זרע לצדקה פסקים ושאלות תשובות* (Responsa of Maharam Padua; Venice: A. Bragadin, 1553), §84, p. 132b.

influence of the equivalent construction in Italian. It soon spread to Poland,⁷¹ and from the 17th century it became quite prevalent in Hebrew. Equivalent forms without the presentative, such as *ani* + infinitive, never arose in Hebrew because they lack a finite element to indicate the tense, and Hebrew does not allow this in verbal sentences.

Table 3 summarizes the development of the presentatives' syntactic structure during the Interim period:

Structure / period	Classic Hebrew	Interim period	Notes
<i>hinne</i> ni + participle	+	+	
<i>hinne</i> ni + nominal predicate	+	+	This structure became more common compared to Classic Hebrew because the emergence of the copular function
<i>hinne</i> ni alone	+	+	
<i>hinne</i> ni + past/future form	+	+	Restricted to present-tense utterances
<i>hinne</i> ni + infinitive	–	+	

Table 3: the structure of the forms in the Interim Period

To conclude this section, we see that *hinne*ni and *hare*ni underwent several changes in the course of the Interim period: First, they lost the rhetorical function of strengthening the certainty of a future action, and, as a result, ceased to occur in future-time sentences and became restricted to present time. Second, their function as markers of immediacy became more pronounced and significantly more prevalent. Third, they came to function as inflected copulas in nominal sentences, which involved a reanalysis of their structure. Fourth, they developed the new function of signaling readiness to perform an action. Finally, they began appearing in a new construction, *hinne*ni + infinitive, with an infinitive predicate. At the end of the Interim period, these forms were thus associated with a number of functions and constructions, all of which were at the disposal of the writers of Hebrew. *Hinne*ni + participle was the most

71. 'הגני להשיב I am responding' (R. Moses Isserles, ספר שאלות ותשובות [Responsa of Rama]; Hamburg: I. H. de Cordoba, 1710), §83, p. 77b.

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prevalent construction, but *hinneni/hareni* could also occur with an infinitive verb or a nominal predicate (noun phrase, adjective phrase or prepositional phrase). All of these constructions expressed present time, even in the rare cases where *hinneni/hareni*, serving as the subject, co-occurred with a finite verb in the past-tense or future-tense forms.

5. THE GRAMMAR OF THE FORMS IN MODERN HEBREW

The revival Period introduced no changes in the functions or distribution of *hinneni/hareni*. They appeared in the same constructions and as they did in the era immediately preceding the revival, as illustrated by Table 4:⁷²

Structure / period	Classic Hebrew	Interim period	Revival period	Example number
<i>hinneni</i> + participle	+	+	+	36
<i>hinneni</i> + nominal predicate	+	+	+	34, 35
<i>hinneni</i> alone	+	+	+	40
<i>hinneni</i> + past/future form	+	+	+	38, 39
<i>hinneni</i> + infinitive	–	+	+	37

Table 4: The structure of the forms in the Revival period

As for the functions, they served the same four functions as in the Interim period:

Function/ period	Classic Hebrew	Interim period	Revival period	Example number
Deictic Function	+	+	+	40
Marker of immediacy	+	+	+	36–39
Marker of futurate action	+	–	–	–
Copula	–	+	+	35
Readiness to perform an action	–	+	+	34

Table 5: The function of the forms in the Revival Period

72. For more on *hinneni* and *hareni* in Modern Hebrew, see M. Ariel, “Givenness Marking,” (Ph.D. dissertation; Tel Aviv University, 1985), p. 297 and M. Ariel, “Three Grammaticalization Paths.”

34. **הנני למצותיך** - ענה מנשה בקול דממה.⁷³
I am ready [to carry out] your commands, said Menashe silently.⁷³
35. עתה **הנני** בת שלשים וחמש.⁷⁴
Today I am 35 years old.⁷⁴
36. **הנני** מודיע לכבודו הרם שגם הנדיב הידוע אין לו עוד שטרי מכירה.⁷⁵
I hereby inform your honor that even the Renowned Benefactor no longer has certificates of sale.⁷⁵
37. **הריני** להודיע לכל בעלי הפרות שישנה בנתניה מחלת הפה והטלפים.⁷⁶
I hereby inform all the owners of cows that there is hoof and mouth disease in Netanya.⁷⁶
38. **והנני אעיר** פה דברים מעטים על אודות חולד אחד, שגדלתיו בביתי.⁷⁷
I make (lit. will make) a few comments here about a mole that I grew in my home.⁷⁷
39. **והנני באתי** להודיעך, שאני וכל בני ביתי בחיים.⁷⁸
And I come (lit. came) to inform you that I and all members of my household are alive.⁷⁸
40. **הריני** פה כְּלִי.⁷⁹
I am all here.⁷⁹

The uses and distribution of *hinnenī* and *harenī* in this period indicate that, in this context, Modern Hebrew until 1920s continued the period that preceded it, namely the Interim period, rather than the Classical period. This is evident from the fact that the functions and the syntactic structures used in the Interim period continued to be used during the Revival period, while the structures and functions that disappeared in the Interim period did not reappear in Modern Hebrew: The deictic function and the function of signaling immediacy, which originate in Classical Hebrew and persisted in the Interim period, survived in Modern Hebrew; conversely, the rhetorical

73. P. Smolenskin, התועה בדרכי החיים (The Wanderer in the Paths of Life; Wien: J. Schlossberg, 1869), 1, p. 86.

74. D. Frischmann, "ביום הכפורים" (On the Day of Atonement), in *Ha-Boker Or* 5 (1880), p. 343.

75. Y. H. Brenner, "במקום ביבליוגרפיה" (In Place of a Bibliography), in *Ha-'adama* 1 (1920), p. 620.

76. Tz. Phikovitch, Muxtar of Netanya, Ephemera Collection, The National Library of Israel, announcement No. 60, September 29, 1939.

77. Mendele Mocher Sforim, תולדות הטבע (Natural History; Leipzig: C. W. Vollrath, 1862), 1, pp. 140–141.

78. Mendele Mocher Sforim, "האבות והבנים" (Fathers and Sons), in *kol kitve mendele* (Odessa: Va'ad Ha-Yovel, 1912), p. 237.

79. U. N. Gnesin, "בטרם" (Beforehand), in *Reshafim* 45 (1910), p. 55.

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function of emphasizing the certainty of a future action, which also originates in the Classical period but did not persist in the Interim period, is absent from Modern Hebrew, even though it was theoretically familiar to the speakers of the early modern language from the Classical texts.

5.1 Linguistic Developments in Modern Hebrew

Although early Modern Hebrew inherited all the uses and constructions of the presentatives from the Interim period, this material did not remain unchanged. Over time, new synchronic patterns emerged: certain constructions and meanings were discarded and distinctions of register were formed.⁸⁰

5.1.1 The Disappearance of Constructions and Function

One of the prominent processes that characterized the crystallization of Modern Hebrew, not only in this context but in general, is a disappearing of the large inventory of constructions and meanings inherited from the earlier stages.⁸¹ In the case of the presentatives, Modern Hebrew discarded the function of signaling readiness to perform an action. Maskilic and revival era literature contain instances of this use (34), but later texts do not.

Moreover, the irregular constructions with verbs in past or future form when referring to present time persisted in the early stages of Modern Hebrew (38, 39), but not in subsequent stages.⁸²

80. On the regularization process in Modern Hebrew, see e.g., Y. Reshef, *Historical Continuity*, and M. Bar-Ziv Levy, "Regularization of Modern Hebrew."

81. Y. Reshef, העברית בתקופת המנדט (Hebrew in the Mandate Period; Jerusalem: Academy of the Hebrew Language, 2015), pp. 40–71.

⁸² Such constructions are occasionally encountered in contemporary Hebrew, but they are not usual in the language and stem from hyper-correction, e.g., הנני הפסקתי ללכת לרופאים 'I stopped going to doctors' (tikiyat-maamarim.com) הנך תתבקש לבחור שם משתמש וסיסמא, 'You will be prompted to choose a username and password' (shlachli.co.il). הינם יחושו נוח וטוב...העבודה שלהם יגדל...הינם יחושו נוח וטוב 'The employees will feel better and more comfortable, and this will even increase their productivity...They will feel much more comfortable and good at your workplace, and in this manner you will increase the opportunities to [acquire] new clients'. These examples, and others, show that among some speakers presentatives appearing without an independent pronoun underwent another reanalysis, and came to be used as alternative forms of the independent pronoun, uninflected for tense.

5.1.2 Register Distinctions

On the eve of the revival period, *hinneni* and *hareni* were fairly prevalent in written Hebrew, and in the initial stages of the revival they remained quite common in literary and administrative texts, in letters and ads, and in the press. They never became part of the spoken language, however, but became associated with the written register. Today they are used as markers of high register, especially in writing, as in examples 41, where they essentially serve as high-register variants of the default independent pronoun *ani*. They are especially typical of texts produced by inexperienced writers trying to elevate their style.⁸³

41. **הנני** נהג חדש

I am a new driver.⁸⁴

In addition, the construction *hinneni* + infinitive, which in the Interim period served to express immediacy in performative and declarative utterances, continued to fulfill this function in Modern Hebrew as well (37). However, whereas in the Interim period, the Maskilic period and the revival period it occurred in a variety of written genres, including literary texts (42, 43).

42. **והנני** לגלות לך סוד כמוס בלבבי

I now reveal to you a secret that is hidden in my heart.⁸⁵

43. אם לרפאל אתה הולך, **הנני** ללוותך

If you are going to Rafael's, I will accompany you.⁸⁶

In later Modern Hebrew it became less common and restricted to the formal register:⁸⁷ official documents and letters, court proceedings, and the like. As a result, it generally co-occurs with a limited inventory of verbs that are typical of this register, such as להודיע 'announce,' להצהיר 'declare' and לצרף 'append,' but never with verbs like לגלות 'reveal,' and ללוות 'accompany' (42, 43).

83. I thank Uri Mor for helping to sharpen this insight.

84. mraavid.co.il

85. P. Smolenskin, "קבורת המור" (A Donkey's Burial), in *Ha-Shahar* 4 (1873), p. 673.

86. Mendele Mocher Sforim, "בעמק הבכא" (In the Valley of Tears), in *Ha-Shiloah* 4 (1898), p. 408.

87. K. Dubnov, "Aviezer."

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This process is illustrated by the following graphs from Google Ngram:

Graph 1: *hinneni* reveal.INF

Graph 2: *hinneni* bring.INF

Graph 3: *hinneni* confirm.INF

Graph 4: *hinneni* announce.INF

The first two graphs show decrease in frequency of *hinneni* + infinitive when the verb is not part of to the formal register, while the third and the fourth graphs show that there is no significant change in frequency of this structure when the verbs are part of to the formal register.

6. CONCLUSION

This study surveyed the functions of *hinneni* and *hareni* throughout the history of the Hebrew language, as well as the syntactic constructions in which they appear. It showed that these functions and constructions underwent a number of changes. Some of the major changes took place during the Interim period of Hebrew, including:

- The loss of the rhetorical function of emphasizing the certainty of a future action in futurate utterances. As a result, the particles stopped appearing in utterances expressing future time and became restricted to utterances expressing present time.
- Enhancement of the particles' role as markers of immediacy in explicit performatives and in declarative utterances.

- The emergence of a copular role of marking tense in nominal sentences, not only in first person but in other persons as well. This involved a syntactic reanalysis of the forms.
- The emergence of the construction *hinneni* + infinitive, with an infinitive predicate.

All of these changes were absorbed into Modern Hebrew along with Classical functions and constructions, but only those which persisted in the Interim period, such as the deictic function and the *hinneni* + participle construction. In other words, in this context Modern Hebrew continued the Interim period. The main process that occurred in Modern Hebrew was a regularization of the material inherited from the preceding stage of the language. This process involved two major aspects: a culling of constructions and meanings, and the emergence of register differentiations.

The linguistic discussion of this topic yields two important insights. First, it demonstrates that there is a continuous line of development extending from the Classical period, through the Interim period to Modern Hebrew. Although the behavior of the presentative particles in Modern Hebrew is different from their behavior in Classical Hebrew, there is no rift between the two eras, but rather continuous development. Moreover, the contribution of the Interim period to the evolution of the particles was more significant than that of Modern Hebrew. Most of the uses of *hinneni* and *hareni* in Modern Hebrew arose in the Interim period, while the modern language only reorganized the inherited material. Although Hebrew in the Interim period had no native speakers, it thrived as a written tongue in which many texts were composed. This preserved its vibrancy and allowed it to continue evolving and producing innovations, some of which persisted in the post-revival period.

Second, this paper also shows that the relationship between Modern Hebrew and its sources cannot be discussed without addressing the Interim period. Studying this period is crucial to understanding the development of Modern Hebrew, and describing the state of Hebrew during this era is an integral part of the research. Ignoring it can lead to mistaken conclusions. Had the present study focused only on comparing the Modern period to the Classical sources, it might have concluded that the changes mentioned above, the various new structures and functions, all arose in the modern era. This could have led to the conclusion that there is a blatant discontinuity between

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Modern Hebrew and the earlier stages of the language, which is not the case. The case of the presentatives reflects an ongoing development, with Modern Hebrew drawing its materials from both the Classical and the Interim eras, without any schism or discontinuity. The conclusion therefore is that, in exploring the development of Modern Hebrew and the question of continuity, it is important not to overlook, or underestimate the significance of, the Interim period.